

Infrastructure, Trade facilitation and Morocco's participation in global value chains: Evidence from ARDL bounds testing approach

Infrastructure, facilitation des échanges et participation du Maroc aux chaînes de valeur mondiales : Une analyse par l'approche ARDL *bounds testing*

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ABSTRACT:

Morocco's participation in global value chains has increased considerably in recent decades. This can be attributed to improved infrastructure, which has enhanced logistics and product transshipment. Trade facilitation measures have also played a key role in accessing international markets. The aim of this article is to provide empirical evidence of the relation between infrastructure, trade facilitation and Morocco's participation in global value chains. In this regard, the application of the ARDL model was appropriate for the object of the study and the nature of the data used. Empirical results show a positive relationship between infrastructure improvements and backward and forward participation. Trade facilitation through lower trade costs and non-tariff measures contributes positively to improving this participation. Based on the results obtained, practical policy implications are discussed.

Keywords: Global value chains; Infrastructure; Trade facilitation; ARDL bounds testing approach.

RESUME :

La participation du Maroc aux chaînes de valeur mondiales a considérablement augmenté au cours des dernières décennies. Cette progression est attribuée à l'amélioration des infrastructures, qui a renforcé la logistique et le transbordement des produits. Les mesures de facilitation des échanges ont également joué un rôle clé pour l'accès aux marchés internationaux. L'objet de cet article est de donner des preuves empiriques de cette relation infrastructures, facilitation des échanges et participation du Maroc aux chaînes de valeur mondiales. Dans ce sillage, l'application du modèle ARDL s'est avéré adéquate avec l'objet de l'étude et la nature des données utilisées. Les résultats empiriques montrent une relation positive entre l'amélioration des infrastructures et la participation en amont et en aval. La facilitation des échanges par la baisse des coûts de commerce et des mesures non tarifaires contribue positivement à améliorer cette participation. Sur la base des résultats obtenus, les implications politiques pratiques sont discutées.

Mots-clés : Chaînes de valeur mondiales ; Infrastructure ; Facilitation des échanges ; ARDL bounds testing.

1. INTRODUCTION

The integration of global value chains (GVCs) represents a major challenge for contemporary economies, influencing not only international trade, but also the economic development of nations. GVCs enable countries to specialize in some stages of production, thus promoting an optimal distribution of resources and skills. However, this integration is highly dependent on a number of factors, including the quality of infrastructure, regional trade agreements, non-tariff measures and the costs associated with trade.

Infrastructure plays a key role in facilitating trade within GVCs. Efficient transport and communication infrastructures reduce logistics costs, increase business competitiveness and enable better integration into international trade networks. At the same time, regional trade agreements have emerged as strategic instruments for promoting economic integration. These agreements, which promote the reduction of trade barriers between partner countries, can also reduce non-tariff measures, enhancing market access and stimulating trade.

However, the impact of non-tariff measures on participation in GVCs raises preoccupations. While these measures may aim to protect consumers and the environment, they can also constitute barriers to trade by increasing the costs of entering foreign markets. Harmonization of these measures therefore appears to be a potential solution for minimizing these negative effects, while preserving the objectives of safety and sustainability.

Finally, trade costs, which include not only customs duties but also other costs associated with importing and exporting, directly influence a country's ability to integrate into GVCs. Reducing these costs can significantly improve participation in value chains, particularly for developing countries seeking to integrate into the global economy.

This paper aims to investigate in depth the complex relationship between infrastructure, trade facilitation (represented by its factors RTAs, NTMs and trade costs) and Morocco's participation in GVCs. By analyzing these interactions, we seek to provide insight into the strategies the country can adopt to enhance its participation in GVCs.

The rest of this article is organized as follows. Section 2 reviews the literature. Section 3 presents the methodology and data used. Section 4 provides regression results and an in-depth discussion. Section 5 summarizes the main conclusions of the study and examines the policy implications.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1. Infrastructure and participation in GVCs

production processes that span several borders require efficient logistics. Access to quality infrastructure, such as ports, roads, railroads and airports, plays a crucial role in participation in GVCs. In addition, access to telecommunication technologies is essential for coordinating these often geographically dispersed production processes. The use of the Internet can also facilitate this participation.

Studies show that infrastructure is particularly decisive in the trade of parts and components, more so than in that of finished goods (Fernandes et al., 2022). The modernization of seaport and airport

infrastructures contributes to facilitating insertion into GVCs, which could also improve with the elimination of barriers to entry for ancillary supplies (del Carpio et al., 2022). In developing countries, Kowalski et al. (2015) find that infrastructure quality and internet use have a positive impact on backward GVCs integration. The results of Lanz & Piermartini (2021) confirm that a good transport infrastructure offers an advantage in upstream production stages. On the other hand, Mouanda-Mouanda & Gong (2019) find that infrastructure quality is positively correlated with backward and forward participation; while Cheng et al, (2015) and Bergantino & Spiru (2021) show that the effect of infrastructure is beneficial for participation in GVCs as a whole. In the case of the African continent, Ketu & Wirajing (2024) reveal that infrastructure development favors Africa's participation in GVCs, for both upstream and downstream flows. These results are verified for different types of infrastructure and income groups.

2.2. Trade facilitation and GVCs participation

Trade facilitation plays an essential role in the integration of economies in GVCs. Since GVCs involve the international fragmentation of production processes, effective Trade Facilitation ensures that goods, services and information flow efficiently across borders. The WTO¹ defines trade facilitation as the simplification, modernization and harmonization of processes required for the circulation of goods in international trade. This simplification, boosted by regional trade agreements, reduces trade costs and the number of non-tariff measures applied by different partners.

According to the WTO², regional trade agreements (RTAs) are reciprocal agreements between two or more partners not necessarily located in the same region. These agreements are an effective means of reducing trade barriers between signatory countries (Antràs, 2020). It is important to note that RTAs often go beyond simple customs tariffs and address various non-tariff issues related to the goods and services sectors. Consequently, engagement in these agreements can be expected to foster participation in GVCs.

Fernandes et al (2022) report that EU or ASEAN membership is associated with significantly higher backward participation in GVCs. Kowalski et al. (2015) find that a higher share of imports and exports covered by RTAs is correlated with greater backward participation, although it may also lead to lower forward participation. UNIDO (2019) argues that economies with more trade covered by trade agreements are better integrated into both backward and forward GVCs. Likewise, Chakrabarty & Chanda (2021) show that an increase in the number of partners in trade agreements promotes greater backward and forward participation.

Non-tariff measures (NTMs) oblige exporters to comply with technical regulations relating to consumer safety and the environment before gaining access to foreign markets. These measures are often used to protect the domestic market, particularly in the context of multilateral and preferential trade agreements aimed at reducing or eliminating tariffs (Bacchetta & Beverelli, 2012). In the context of GVCs, NTMs can curb imports of inputs needed for exports, thereby reducing backward participation. They can also increase the cost of imported inputs, negatively impacting forward participation. Franssen & Solleder's (2016) analysis of the effects of NTMs on GVCs participation

¹ WTO (2024). Trade facilitation. Accessed October 21, 2024, from :

https://www.wto.org/english/tratop_e/tradfa_e/tradfa_e.htm

² WTO (2024). Regional Trade Agreements. Accessed October 21, 2024, from :

https://www.wto.org/English/Tratop_E/region_e/scope_rta_e.htm

suggests a negative correlation between these measures and GVCs participation. Ghodsi & Stehrer (2016), meanwhile, show a positive influence of regulations on the performance of non-services industries when integrated into trade agreements. More recently, Kim (2021) indicates that lack of harmony between NTMs hinders backward but favors forward participation. He proposes harmonizing these measures rather than eliminating them altogether in order to reduce transaction costs in the long term.

The emergence of GVCs has been facilitated by a general decline in trade costs. These costs can arise from a variety of factors, such as geographical remoteness, inefficient infrastructure or regulatory barriers. In sequential GVCs, these costs accumulate along the value chain, having a more significant impact on downstream than on upstream stages (Antràs, 2020). Moreover, bilateral value-added flows depend not only on bilateral trade costs, but also on those linked to the third countries through which this value-added transits (Noguera, 2012). Thus, it appears that these costs tend to hinder both backward and forward participation in GVCs.

3. DATA AND METHODOLOGY

3.1. Data

To test the relationship between backward and forward participation as endogenous variables and infrastructure, and trade facilitation as exogenous variables, we examine annual data for Morocco over the period 1990-2019, the longest possible period offered by the UNCTAD-Eora GVC database. The table below shows the data sources used:

Table 1: Data source

Variable	Description	Source
BP	Backward participation in GVCs represented by foreign value-added content as a percentage of gross exports	Eora-GVC
FP	Forward participation in GVCs represented by local value-added content in partners' exports as a percentage of gross exports	Eora-GVC
RTA	Regional Trade Agreements signed by Morocco	WTO RTA-IS
TC	Trade costs calculated from FOB-CAF data, expressed as a percentage of trade	IMF
NTM	Non-tariff measures implemented by Morocco	WTO
PT	Port traffic is total port traffic in millions of tons	ANP
IU	Internet Usage is the percentage of the population using the Internet	BM
RERM	Real Exchange Rate Misalignment expressed as a deviation from the equilibrium level	CEPII

Source: Elaborated by the author

Table 2 shows the descriptive statistics for the variables included in our models. Over the period 1990-2019, average backward and forward participation is 13.89% and 36.31% respectively. The maximum backward and forward participation is recorded in 2019 and 2006 respectively, while the minimum is recorded in 1998 and 1990 respectively. This means that Morocco's participation increased in the 2000s compared with the 90s, with a rise in backward participation against a downward trend in forward participation.

For RTAs, Morocco has concluded agreements with its trading partners that have grown from a single agreement in 1990 to eight agreements in 2019, and which aim, among other things, to abolish customs tariffs. However, the growth of these RTAs has been accompanied by an increase in the number of NTMs applied by Morocco, reaching 21 measures in 2019. Trade costs, which represent one of the main determinants of international trade, account on average for 12.65% of Morocco's trade. However, these costs fell significantly in the 2000s, with an average of 10.95%, compared with 16.03% in the 1990s. Connectivity indicators show that average port traffic is 60.89 million tones, with a minimum value of 40.31 million tones recorded in 1990 and a maximum value of 88.01 recorded in 2019. The percentage of the population connected to the Internet, which was close to 0% in 1990, reached 74.38% in 2019, attesting to the improvement in access to information and communication technologies. The data also show that the real exchange rate is misaligned from its equilibrium level, meaning that the RER is undervalued.

Table 2: Descriptive Statistics

Variable	Obs.	Mean	Min.	Max.	Std. Dev.	Jarque-Bera (Prob.)
BP (%)	30	13.89	10.39	20.31	3.01	0.233
FP (%)	30	36.31	23.84	42.43	5.51	0.076
RTA	30	5.00	1.00	8.00	3.02	0.162
TC (%)	30	12.65	7.00	20.36	3.47	0.074
NTM	30	4.00	0.00	21.00	5.49	0.001
PT (MT)	30	60.89	40.31	88.01	15.06	0.421
IU (%)	30	24.44	0.00	74.38	26.64	0.152
RERM (%)	30	-10.37	-20.83	1.42	4.88	0.866

Source: Elaborated by the author

The relationship between RTAs, trade costs, NTMs, infrastructure and GVCs participation in Morocco can be analyzed using the analytical framework developed by Ahmed et al. (2017) and Ignatenko et al. (2019). The regression model is defined by equations (1) and (2) below:

$$BP_t = f(RTA_t, TC_t, NTM_t, PT_t, IU_t, RERM_t) \quad (1)$$

$$FP_t = f(RTA_t, TC_t, NTM_t, PT_t, IU_t, RERM_t) \quad (2)$$

Backward and Forward participation in GVCs represent the endogenous variables. The exogenous variables include RTAs, TC and NTMs as proxies for trade facilitation, PT and IU as proxies for infrastructure. RERM is used as a control variable.

3.2. ARDL model

Pesaran & Shin, (1998) proposed a cointegration analysis based on an ARDL (AutoRegressive Distributed Lag) model to examine long-run relationships when independent variables are integrated in order I(1). Pesaran et al (2001) have developed a new, more flexible and less restrictive method for testing the existence of a long-run relationship between variables using the ARDL bounds test. There are several reasons for using this model in time series. Firstly, the bounds test is applicable for integrated variables of order I(0) or order I(1) or a combination between the two, but no variable should be integrated of order I(2) (Pesaran et al., 2001). Secondly, this method is suitable for small sample sizes (Narayan, 2005). Finally, the ARDL cointegration method offers the possibility of dealing with both long-term and short-term relationships between variables (Sloboda, 2004).

Consequently, the cointegration model based on the ARDL bounds test is as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta y_t = & \alpha_0 + \lambda_1 y_{t-1} + \lambda_2 RTA_{t-1} + \lambda_3 TC_{t-1} + \lambda_4 NTM_{t-1} + \lambda_5 PT_{t-1} + \lambda_6 IU_{t-1} + \lambda_7 RERM_{t-1} \\ & + \sum_{i=1}^p \beta_{1i} \Delta y_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^{q_1} \beta_{2i} \Delta RTA_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^{q_2} \beta_{3i} \Delta TC_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^{q_3} \beta_{4i} \Delta NTM_{t-i} \\ & + \sum_{i=0}^{q_4} \beta_{5i} \Delta PT_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^{q_5} \beta_{6i} \Delta IU_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^{q_7} \beta_{7i} \Delta RERM_{t-i} + \mu_t \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

With Δ is the first differences operator; y_t is the endogenous variable representing either backward or forward participation; $\lambda_1 - \lambda_7$ are the long-term relationships; $\beta_{1i} - \beta_{7i}$ represent the short-term dynamics of the model; α_0 and μ_t represent the constant and error term, respectively; p is the number of lags of the explained variable and q is the number of lags of the explanatory variables.

In addition, we apply the bounds test approach to check if there is a long-run equilibrium between the variables. Once the long-run relationship has been validated, we use OLS to estimate the coefficients of the long-run relationships and the short-run dynamics.

4. RESULTS

We present the results of the unit root tests, the bounds test and the validation tests before presenting the long-term relationships and short-term dynamics.

4.1. Unit root test

Before proceeding with the ARDL approach, we test the stationarity of the different series to ensure that none of them is integrated of order greater than one. To do this, we use the ADF test (Dickey & Fuller, 1979), the PP test (Phillips & Perron, 1988) and the KPSS test (Kwiatkowski et al., 1992). The results are as follows:

Table 3: Unit root test result

Variables	ADF	PP	KPSS
BP	-2.9154	-1,1548	0.1776
Δ BP	-3.7639**	-3,9495**	0.0828**
FP	-0.7996	-0.5854	0.1851
Δ FP	-5.9126***	-5.8911***	0.0674**
RTA	-0.8050	-1.1434	0.1280**
Δ RTA	-3.7276**	-3.7225**	-
TC	-3.8255**	-3.0090	0.0756**
Δ TC	-	-6.3982***	-
NTM	-2.8350	-2.8460	0.1262**
Δ NTM	-4.0077**	-5.2061***	-
PT (Log)	-3.0789	-3.0609	0.1159
Δ PT (Log)	-6.7059***	-7.3918***	0.1061**
IU	-1.7346	-1.7346	0.1549
Δ IU	-5.2167***	-5.2194***	0.1211**
RERM	-2.3916	-1.9337	0.1149**
Δ RERM	-4.6427***	-4.7945***	-

(***) and (**) indicate rejection of the null hypothesis of non-stationarity at the 1% and 5% levels respectively for the ADF and PP tests, and non-rejection of the null hypothesis of stationarity for the KPSS test.

Source: Elaborated by the author

The results of the three tests show that the series are stationary in level or first difference. This combination of integrated series of order I(0) and order I(1) justifies the choice of the ARDL model.

4.2. Bounds test

The bounds test is a cointegration test proposed by Pesaran et al. (2001) to verify the existence of a long-term relationship between variables. The results of this test are presented in Table 4 below:

Table 4: Bounds test result

Dependent variable	k	F-stat	Critical values 1%		Critical values 5%	
			I(0)	I(1)	I(0)	I(1)
BP	6	6.097**	4.27	6.211	2.97	4.499
FP	6	5.406***	2.66	4.05	2.04	3.24

(***) and (**) indicate rejection of the null hypothesis at the 1% and 5% levels, respectively. "k" is the number of exogenous variables. I(0) and I(1) represent the lower and upper bounds, respectively.

Source: Elaborated by the author

The Fisher statistic calculated is above the upper bound at the 5% threshold for the first model and at the 1% threshold for the second model. Consequently, the null hypothesis of no cointegration is

rejected, and the existence of a long-term relationship between the variables in the models studied is confirmed.

Based on these results, we can estimate the long-term relationship and short-term dynamics between the different variables.

4.3. Empirical results and discussion

The long-term results show that the number of RTAs has a negative impact on backward participation and a positive impact on forward participation. This result can be explained by the nature of trade flows under these agreements. Indeed, Morocco's imports under the trade agreements consist mainly of finished products for final consumption, whereas Morocco's exports under the agreements consist mainly of commodities and intermediate products. Worse still, RTAs aim to remove tariff measures as barriers to trade, while non-tariff measures are still outside the scope of such agreements. As a result, countries are increasingly practicing non-tariff measures to limit their imports or for other reasons such as the protection of human, animal and plant life (Ghodsi et al., 2017). Consequently, our results confirm the existence of a negative relationship between the number of NTMs applied by Morocco and its backward participation. Furthermore, the impact of these NTMs is also negative on Morocco's forward participation in GVCs. This result can be explained by the fact that, under GVCs, local value added in exports depends, among other things, on foreign value added in exports (Lopez Gonzalez, 2016), and so measures that curb imports of foreign inputs will also curb exported domestic inputs. The results of (Khouilid, 2019) go in the same direction, showing that non-tariff measures negatively affect Moroccan foreign trade. The results also show a negative and significant relationship between real exchange rate misalignment and forward participation which means that an undervaluation of the RER relative to its equilibrium level improves the competitiveness of exported domestic inputs and beyond increases the forward participation of GVCs. This result is confirmed by the work of (Patel et al., 2019) and (Ahmed et al., 2017), which show a negative relationship between the real exchange rate and export competitiveness.

As expected, there is a negative relationship between trade costs (transport, insurance, etc.) and participation in GVCs. Indeed, one of the main causes of the rise of GVCs is the fall in trade costs, which makes this new form of organization possible, resulting in particular in an increase in the number of border crossings required to complete a finished product (Guilhoto et al., 2019). Another cause of the rise of GVCs is the development of means of transport and telecommunication, which facilitate the coordination of sequences of spatially dispersed activities. Our results confirm this relationship for the case of Morocco and show a positive impact of the increase in port traffic, an indicator of the development of means of transport, and the increase in the number of internet users, an indicator of the development of telecommunications, on its participation in GVCs.

Table 5 then reports the short-term dynamics resulting from the error-correction specifications of the ARDL models. The estimated coefficients of the error-correction terms (ECM) are negative and significant at the 1% level, confirming the existence of a convergence mechanism towards the long-term target. These coefficients are estimated at 84% for the first specification and 57% for the second specification, reflecting a relatively rapid adjustment to the long-term target for forward participation and a very rapid adjustment for backward participation.

The short-term results remain virtually identical to those for the long term. We observe that backward participation depends positively on its past values. This result can be explained by the positive backward participation rate observed in recent years. On the other hand, we observe that forward participation depends negatively on its differentiated values in t-1 and t-2, and positively on its value in t-3.

In the short term, increasing the number of RTAs reduces the backward participation rate and increases the forward participation rate, which is in line with the long-term relationships. The same applies to trade costs, which are falling, leading to increased backward and forward participation in GVCs. For NTMs, increasing application has a negative impact on backward participation. On the other hand, their impact on forward participation is positive in the short term. This result shows that a short-term logic leads to false reasoning about the role of DTMs, which are seen as advantageous for improving the level of participation forward of GVCs, but in reality are constraining in the long term.

As far as port traffic is concerned, the results confirm its positive effect on both backward and forward participation. A surprising result concerns the number of Internet users, which has a negative short-term impact on participation in GVCs. Internet use has a positive short-term impact on forward participation. Indeed, companies need new technologies to connect to GVCs. Investment in technology and infrastructure is therefore necessary to take full advantage of specialization and higher-quality imported inputs in the context of GVCs (Gentile et al., 2021).

Table 5: Long- and short-term relations estimated using the ARDL approach

Dep. Variable (y)	Backward Participation	Forward Participation
	ARDL (2,0,1,1,1,1,0)	ARDL (4,1,2,2,2,1,0)
Long-term relations estimated using the ARDL model		
<i>RTA</i>	-0.0193** (0.011)	-0.0007 (0.897)
<i>TC</i>	-0.3298** (0.017)	-0.2172 (0.147)
<i>NMT</i>	-0.0044** (0.034)	-0.0033** (0.037)
<i>PT</i>	0.1770* (0.060)	0.0970*** (0.000)
<i>IU</i>	0.2024*** (0.000)	-0.0855 (0.141)
<i>RERM</i>	0.0569 (0.604)	-0.2294*** (0.008)

Table 5: Long- and short-term relations estimated using the ARDL approach (continued)

Dep. Variable (y)	Backward Participation	Forward Participation
	ARDL (2,0,1,1,1,1,0)	ARDL (4,1,2,2,2,1,0)
Short-term relations derived from ARDL model		
<i>Constant</i>	-0.3918*** (0.000)	-
Δy_{t-1}	0.2836** (0.027)	-0.5816*** (0.003)
Δy_{t-2}	-	-0.2453* (0.094)
Δy_{t-3}	-	0.6248*** (0.001)
ΔRTA_t	-	0.0158*** (0.002)
ΔTC_t	-0.1144* (0.068)	-0.3333*** (0.002)
ΔTC_{t-1}	-	-0.1949** (0.031)
ΔNMT_t	-0.0013*** (0.005)	-0.0002 (0.555)
ΔNMT_{t-1}	-	0.0025*** (0.002)
ΔPT_t	0.0584** (0.036)	0.1387*** (0.000)
ΔPT_{t-1}	-	0.0934** (0.012)
ΔIU_t	0.0337 (0.414)	0.0923* (0.069)
ECM_{t-1}	-0.8420*** (0.000)	-0.5684*** (0.000)
<i>Diagnostic tests</i>		
Adjusted R ²	0.898	0.942
Jarque-Bera	0.367 (0.832)	0.284 (0.868)
LM (1)	1.450 (0.229)	1.247 (0.264)
BPG	6.994 (0.858)	20.612 (0.299)
ARCH (1)	0.000 (0.999)	0.000 (0.991)
Ramsey RESET	1.791 (0.202)	1.954 (0.205)

(***), (**), (*) indicate the significance of coefficients at the 1%, 5% and 10% levels respectively. Values in brackets are p-values.

Source: Elaborated by the author

We conducted diagnostic tests to assess the robustness of our models: the Jarque-Bera test for residual normality, the Lagrange Multiplier (LM) test for residual autocorrelation, the Breusch-Pagan-Godfrey (BPG) and ARCH tests for heteroscedasticity, and the Ramsey Functional Form Test (RESET).

The results show that the models are of good quality, since the values of the adjusted R^2 statistics are close to one. The validity tests confirm the normality of the residuals, the absence of autocorrelation and the absence of heteroscedasticity, since the p-values of the tests are all greater than 5%. The Ramsey test also shows that the functional form of our specifications is correct.

In addition, we performed the CUSUM test and the CUSUM of squares test to check the stability of model parameters. The results presented below show that the estimated parameters are stable over the study period.

Figure 1: CUSUM and CUSUM of squares tests

Source: Elaborated by the author

5. Conclusion

This paper aims to investigate the relationship between infrastructures, trade facilitation, Morocco's participation in GVCs. Infrastructure is proxied by port traffic volume, and internet usage obtained

from ANP and World Bank databases. Trade facilitation is represented by the cost of trade, regional trade agreements and non-tariff measures obtained from WTO and IMF databases. Morocco's participation in GVCs is measured simultaneously by backward and forward participation taken from the Eora-GVC database.

After estimating the ARDL model and verifying long-term relationships and short-term dynamics, the results show that infrastructure enhances Morocco's participation in GVCs in both the short and long term. Trade facilitation through lower trade costs and non-tariff measures contributes positively to improving this participation in both the short and long term. However, the number of regional trade agreements deteriorates backward participation in the long term, and only improves forward participation in the short term. To strengthen its position in the GVCs, Morocco must continue to invest in infrastructure and harmonize its non-tariff measures, while diversifying its trade partnerships.

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